

D4.2 – Lunar Raw Water Simulant

prepared for

WP4.2 – Lunar Raw Water and Ice Simulant Development

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1 Lunar Raw Water Simulant

Lunar raw water simulants, which are water polluted with volatiles and other compounds, have been developed for different purposes of subsystem and system testing within LUWEX.

NOTE: A detailed description of the development process and the decisions made that resulted in the final raw water simulant combinations can be found in deliverable D4.4 Simulant Development Report.

The following table shows the compositions of the different raw water simulants.

Simulant	Purpose	Composition					
			CH ₃ OH	NH ₃	SO ₂	CO ₂	Regolith Dust
Lunar raw water simulants C3, C4, C5, C6, C7, C8 (6 L bulk solution)	Subsystem testing	C3	20.17 µL			*	
		C4			9.73 µL	*	
		C5		77.42 µL		*	
		C6		77.42 µL	9.73 µL	*	
		C7	20.17 µL	77.42 µL	9.73 µL	*	
		C8	20.17 µL	77.42 µL	9.73 µL	*	1 g
Lunar raw water simulant E1 (25 L bulk solution)	Ice production for system testing	E1	377 mL			574.5 g	**

*CO₂ concentration equals equilibrium of dissolved CO₂ from atmosphere.

**Will be mixed with several kilograms of Lunar Regolith Simulant in various ratios.

Simulants C3 to C8 have been supplied to TAS and PWR for subsystem testing beginning of October 2023. The simulants were sent in 250 mL badges of stock solution which need to be topped up with ultra-pure water to a 6 L bulk solution.

Simulant E1 will be supplied to TUBS in November 2023 for Ice production testing and also in February 2024 for the system test campaign.

Figure 1-1: Raw water simulant stock solution before shipment to project partners.